

IMPORTANCE OF MEDICINAL PLANTS ON HUMAN HEALTH IN PREVENTING VARIOUS DISEASES

Rasulov Ilhom Mahmudovich

Associate professor, PhD, doctor of agricultural sciences

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8116741>

Abstract. Writing to this article assist the Decree No. PD-3968 of the President of Uzbekistan dated October 12, 2018 “On measures to regulate the field of folk medicine in the Republic of Uzbekistan”, PD-5707 dated April 10, 2019 “On measures to further develop the pharmaceutical industry of the republic in 2019-2021” Decree No. PD-4670 dated April 10, 2020 “On measures for the protection of wild medicinal plants, cultivation, processing and rational use of available resources” in preventing various diseases in the human body, a the significance of several medicinal plants was studied.

Keywords: *artemisia, alhagi, zizifora, herba bursae pastoris, plantago, harmalae, cichorium intybus, taraxacum, helichrysum arenarium, common yarrow, salvia, capparis, ferula, angina, tonsillitis, stomatitis, purulent otitis, anthelmintic, antiseptic, diaphoretic.*

Introduction. There are about 500,000 plant species on earth, and 6,000 of them are used. The nature of Uzbekistan stands out in the world with its uniqueness, plants, clear waters, mountains, forests, mineral resources, soil, air and inexhaustible aspects. There are more than 4650 species of wild plants, of which there are 577 medicinal plants, 103 medicinal plants with dyes, and 560 essential oil medicinal plants. It has been determined that there are 10-12 thousand species of medicinal plants on earth. The chemical and pharmacological properties of more than 1200 plant species have been investigated. These are 40-48%. So, it can be seen that the raw materials of medicinal plants have been used for centuries to restore human health. Medicinal plants are mainly dried: herbs, shoots, roots, rhizomes, buds, bulbs, bark, leaves, flowers, buds, fruits (seeds), seeds, and juice, pulp, essential oils are used to prevent various diseases and restore human health.

The importance of other medicinal plants for human health is presented in the table. For example: Glycyrrhiza, artemisia, alhagi, zizifora, herba bursae pastoris, plantago, harmalae, cichorium intybus, taraxacum.

Importance of several medicinal plants for human health in preventing various diseases

Scientific name of medicinal plants	Importance for human health
1. Glycyrrhiza - (Glerrhizza glabra L.) a perennial plant belonging to the leguminous family.	Glycyrrhiza and its root juice and powders are used as antiperspirant, mild expectorant, in diseases related to respiratory tract colds, expectorant, and help in shortness of breath. A decoction prepared from its roots has the properties of treating gastric and duodenal ulcers. A decoction of the root is drunk in case of meat and mushroom poisoning.

<p>2. Artemisia - (Artemisia absinthium L.) Asteraceae family, wild perennial herb</p>	<p>A decoction of artemisia is used for respiratory colds, anemia, rheumatism, bronchial asthma and insomnia, invigorates the work of the gastrointestinal tract, increases bile secretion and pancreatic function, and improves digestion. Kills harmful bacteria and fungi contained in food, stimulates the central nervous system and restores heart function, artemisia tincture is also a great help in nervous diseases.</p>
<p>3. Alhagi - a genus of perennial weeds belonging to the legume family.</p>	<p>A decoction (sometimes also a tincture) made from the root of the alhagi root is used to treat hemorrhoids and wounds, to stop bleeding from the stomach (bloody diarrhea) and liver, gastrointestinal ulcer, a tincture made from the body of the alhagi root is used in the above-mentioned diseases and angina, tonsillitis, stomatitis, purulent otitis, nasopharyngitis, uterine ulcer, and as an expectorant, it is also used in the treatment of diarrhea and gastrointestinal diseases.</p>
<p>4. Zizifora – Lamiaceae family, wild herbaceous perennial plant – latin name Ziziphora)-</p>	<p>Angina, myocarditis, a mild form of hypertension, difficulty urinating, chronic nephritis, the tincture is used to reduce the cardiovascular system, arterial blood pressure, urinary tract, in the treatment of liver diseases, especially in the effective treatment of jaundice and hepatitis, when it is difficult to pass sputum, to lower blood pressure, to calm the nerves. , it is used for children with complications of rheumatism, for adults with neurosis, neurasthenia and vascular diseases, when blood pressure increases.</p>
<p>5. Herba bursae pastoris – Brassicaceae family, annual herb</p>	<p>Herba bursae pastoris is used in gynecological practice in the form of a tincture and extract as a postpartum hemostatic agent, as well as to strengthen the contraction of the uterine muscles during childbirth. In the treatment of pulmonary tuberculosis with frequent hemoptysis and bleeding, herba bursae pastoris has been found to be effective. In early spring, young leaves are used to boost immunity and refresh.</p>
<p>6. Plantago- Plantaginaceae family, a large perennial wild and cultivated herb (Plantago major L.)</p>	<p>Medicinal plant Plantago is used as an expectorant, anti-inflammatory, in the treatment of gastrointestinal tract diseases (hypoacidity, enteritis, colitis, duodenal ulcer) and in the treatment of upper respiratory tract infections with cough.</p>

<p>7. Harmalae-Nitrariaceae family, is a perennial herb.</p>	<p>Harmalae for medical purposes, less frankincense seeds, often the herb, are used. Deoxypeganine hydrochloride has anticholinesterase properties and is used in the treatment of various forms of myopathy and myasthenia, chronic constipation, intestinal atony, epidemic encephalitis, tick paralysis and Parkinson's disease from garmin contained in frankincense seeds. , used as an anthelmintic, antiseptic, diaphoretic and diuretic.</p>
<p>8. <i>Cichorium intybus</i> - (<i>Cichorium intybus</i> L.,) Asteraceae family, Perennial plant with erect and thick roots.</p>	<p><i>Cichorium intybus</i> is a valuable medicinal plant that has been popular in folk medicine for a long time. Burdock root was used in ancient Rome to improve digestion, and in Egypt it was used to make anti-venom for snake and spider bites. The famous Abu Ali ibn Sina was used in the treatment of gastrointestinal tract and eye diseases, inflammation of the eyes and gout. In modern medicine, sage has a wide range of uses due to its beneficial medicinal properties (sedative, hypoglycemic, astringent, expectorant, diuretic, anti-inflammatory, antipyretic, anthelmintic).</p>
<p>9. <i>Taraxacum</i> -- (<i>Taraxacum officinale</i> L.,) Asteraceae Compositae family, perennial herb medicinal plant</p>	<p><i>Taraxacum</i> is the best remedy for liver disease, anacid gastritis caused by constipation, gall bladder disease, bile, diuretic, appetite suppressant, blood purifier, suppurative, and gastritis, gout, and skin diseases that develop due to lack of hydrochloric acid in the stomach. Tincture is used in place of a sedative, and the juice of freshly cut leaves is the best remedy for anemia, impotence, and pain in the chest area. A green salad prepared from it refreshes a person and increases his ability to work.</p>
<p>10. <i>Helichrusum maracandicum</i>- is a perennial medicinal plant.</p>	<p>The flowers of the <i>Helichrusum maracandicum</i> are considered gardeners. It is a choleric plant for liver pain, jaundice, gallstone disease, kidney stone disease, asthma, pulmonary tuberculosis, tuberculosis, hemostatic, worm driver (especially ascarida), anti-cold medicinal plant. In scientific medical practice, it is called boznoch. In particular, decoction and tincture made from the flowers of <i>Helichrusum maracandicum</i>, liquid extract is used as a bile-driving factor in liver diseases.</p>

<p>11. Common yarrow - (<i>Achillea millefolium</i> L.) Perennial grass with feathery leaves belonging to the family of the family of sedges.</p>	<p>Common yarrow - extract and tincture are used for the treatment of gastric and intestinal ulcer diseases, to increase appetite and to stop bleeding.</p>
<p>12. <i>Salvia</i> (<i>Salvia officinalis</i> L.,) Lamiaceae family, biennial or perennial herb</p>	<p><i>Salvia</i> is used in medicine for polyarthritis, osteomyelitis, deforming arthrosis, and trophic ulcers. After extracting the essential oil, the remaining raw material mass is used for therapeutic rheumatic baths. <i>Salvia</i> has antibacterial properties. Coumarins in the root have antitumor effects. In <i>salvia</i> folk medicine, it is used for urinary stone disease, rheumatism, and tachycardia, a decoction of the ground part with milk is used as an antipyretic, as well as an aromatic and digestive aid. In skin diseases, <i>salvia</i> oil is used externally by massaging. It is used for dysentery, purulent diseases, thrush, hair loss.</p>
<p>13. <i>Capparis</i>– <i>Capparaceae</i> family perennial plant</p>	<p>The extract from the <i>capparis</i> is a part of the complex drug LIV-52, manufactured in India and approved in medical practice. It is released in the form of tablets and is prescribed for liver disease. Fresh parts of the plant have astringent, diuretic, antiseptic and analgesic properties. Juice wounds, root bark is chewed for toothache. In folk medicine, the fruits of the gourd are used in the treatment of toothache, gum disease, thyroid gland, and hemorrhoids. The bark of the crushed roots is used for gout and brucellosis. Tincture of root bark is used in angina pectoris, nervous seizures, paralysis, rheumatic pains with colds, spleen diseases, liver diseases, including jaundice.</p>
<p>14. <i>Ferula</i>-<i>Ferula celeriac</i> (<i>umbelliferae</i>) - belongs to the <i>Apiaceae</i> (<i>Umbelliferae</i>) family and is a perennial herb</p>	<p><i>Ferula</i>-hepatitis disease, adding pepper and vinegar to its paste and applying it to bad quality wounds is beneficial. Hair loss, gum-resin tuberculosis, plague, wounds, whooping cough, toothache, nervine tonic, expectorant and dewormer, gum-resin as a powder, emulsion and tincture as pain reliever, used in health as an expectorant, tonic and sedative.</p>

REFERENCES

1. Ўзбекистон Президентининг 2018 йил 12 октябрдаги “Ўзбекистон Республикасида халқ таъбири соҳасини тартибга солиш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида” ги ПҚ–3968 сонли қарори

2. 2019 йил 10 апрельдаги “2019-2021 йилларда республиканинг фармацевтика тармоғини янада жадал ривожлантириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида”ги ПФ–5707-сонли фармони
3. 2020 йил 10 апрелдаги ПҚ-4670-сонли ”Ёввойи ҳолда ўсувчи доривор ўсимликларни муҳофаза қилиш, маданий ғолда етиштириш, қайта ишлаш ва мавжуд ресурслардан оқилона фойдаланиш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида”ги қарори
4. Тўхтаев Б.Ё. Ўзбекистоннинг шўр ерларида доривор ўсимликларнинг интродукцияси. //Биология фанлари доктори илмий даражасини олиш учун ёзилган. Автореферати 2009 йил
5. Холматов Х.Х., Қосимов А.И., Доривор ўсимликлар. – Тошкент, Ибн Сино номидаи нашриёт-матбаа бирлашмаси, 1994 йил
6. Холматов Х.Х., Ахмедов У.А. Фармакогнозия: Тиббиёт олий ўқув юртлари талабалари учун дарслик. - Тошкент: Ибн Сино номидаги нашриёт-матбаа бирлашмаси, 1995 йил